

THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF EUCALYPTUS CAMALDULENSIS: AN EVIDENCE-BASED REVIEW

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Abstract

Eucalyptus camaldulensis, the River Red Gum, has emerged as a significant plant species with diverse therapeutic potential. This review synthesizes recent scientific literature (2016-2023) to provide a comprehensive overview of its therapeutic applications, particularly focusing on its antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, and insecticidal properties. The analysis reveals that *E. camaldulensis* exhibits broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity against numerous bacterial and fungal species, as well as antiviral effects against viruses like Varicella-Zoster and Herpes Simplex. Its efficacy as a natural insect repellent against a wide range of pests is also highlighted. Furthermore, the review explores the promising antidiabetic and anticancer properties of *E. camaldulensis* extracts and oils against various cancer cell lines. The traditional and contemporary uses of this plant in oral hygiene, respiratory ailments, and pain relief due to its analgesic properties are also discussed. The multifaceted therapeutic potential of *E. camaldulensis* positions it as a valuable resource for developing natural alternatives to synthetic antimicrobial agents, insecticides, and potentially anticancer therapies. Further research, especially on regional species, is warranted to fully exploit its advantageous traits for medicinal and commercial applications.

Introduction

The over-green perennial *Eucalyptus* tree (*Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, family Myrtaceae), originally imported to Pakistan from Australia, has become an important, extensively dispersed, and widely planted species, now cultivated in 95 countries worldwide (Abdul Hussein Taha and Mohammed, 2023). While its wood is primarily used in the furniture industry, particularly due to

the global shortage of poplar wood, and by farmers as fuel, it also finds applications in the production of plywood, particle board, fiberboard, matchsticks, sporting goods, tables, chairs, mattresses, and various industrial products (Khan et al., 2020; Usman et al., 2022). *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* has become one of Pakistan's most popular tree species, owing to

thorough analyses of its growth traits and wood quality since the early 20th century (Nawaz et al., 2016; Ulla et al., 2022). The leaves, bark, and flowers of Eucalyptus are also sources of essential oils with therapeutic applications (Bisht Kumar and Chandra, 2021).

This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the therapeutic potential of *E. camaldulensis*, focusing on its antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, and insecticidal properties, based on a systematic review of recent scientific literature.

Methodology

A comprehensive literature search was conducted using the research databases Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, Science Direct, Web of Science, and Google Patents. The search focused on publications released between 2016 and May 2023, using the following keywords: "Eucalyptus plant," "therapeutic application," "E. camaldulensis oils and extract," "pharmacological," and "ethnomedicinal." The search included new inventions and medicinal formulations containing *E. camaldulensis*. Repetitive and unpublished data were excluded from the analysis. Based on predefined eligibility criteria, 123 studies were selected from a total of 300 papers.

Antibacterial Activity

E. camaldulensis Leaf extracts represent a valuable source of antibacterial compounds for the pharmaceutical industry (Talha Alnomani and Mirforoughi, 2021). Knezevic et al. (2016) demonstrated the antibacterial efficacy of two essential oils from *E. camaldulensis* against multidrug-resistant (MDR) *Acinetobacter baumannii* wound isolates. The synergistic effects of *E. camaldulensis* essential oils and traditional antibiotics suggest potential for novel therapeutic approaches to infections caused by MDR *A. baumannii* strains.

Extracts of *E. camaldulensis* leaves were also tested for antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at concentrations of 400, 200, 100, and 50 mg/ml. Phytochemical analysis of the leaf

extracts revealed the presence of cardiac glycosides, alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, and saponins. Each extract inhibited all test bacteria, with the highest dose of ethanol extract (400 mg/ml) showing the greatest efficacy against *B. subtilis* (27 mm). Petroleum ether and methanol extracts also demonstrated significant effectiveness. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) for all extracts ranged from 50 to 200 mg/ml. The inhibitory effects of the plant extracts were comparable to those of commercially available antibiotics (Chuku et al., 2016).

E. camaldulensis leaves have also been shown to be effective against food-borne diseases and infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*. *S. aureus* was more susceptible to crude extracts and solvent fractions of *E. camaldulensis* than other bacteria, exhibiting varying degrees of inhibition (Singh and Thakur, 2016). Mervat et al. (2017) evaluated the effectiveness of *E. camaldulensis* bark in inhibiting the growth of four distinct plant pathogenic bacteria: *Dickeya* spp., *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*, *Pectobacterium carotovorum* subsp. *carotovorum*, and *Ralstonia solanacearum*. The bark of *E. camaldulensis* exhibited the highest levels of inhibition at 20.0 and 18.3 mm, with high concentrations of camphor (30.9%), menthol (8.8%), 1,8-cineole (eucalyptol) (8.2%), and 8-nonynoic acid methyl ester (45.6%). Phytochemical extracts from *E. camaldulensis* demonstrated high to moderate antibacterial activity against the plant bacterial pathogens tested.

The antibacterial activity of *E. camaldulensis* leaves and fruit cultivated in Mersin was examined using the agar well diffusion method. The main constituents of the leaf oil were α -pinene (12.7%), α -terpinol (10.7%), eucalyptol (1,8-cineole) (14.1%), and *p*-cymene (42.1%), while the main constituents of the fruit oil were α -terpinol (15.1%), *p*-cymene (30.0%), eucalyptol (1,8-cineole) (34.5%), and α -pinene (9.0%). Both leaf and fruit oils contained high levels of monoterpene hydrocarbons and oxygenated monoterpenes and significantly inhibited the growth of both Gram-positive (*S. aureus*, *Streptococcus* sp., and *B. subtilis*) and Gram-

negative (*Escherichia coli*) bacteria ($p < 0.05$) (Dogan et al., 2017).

Elansary et al. (2017) reported that *E. camaldulensis* extracts exhibited the highest phenolic content, antioxidant activity, and antibacterial activity compared to other cultivars. The MIC values for the antibacterial activity of *E. camaldulensis* ranged from 0.08 g/mL (*Bacillus cereus*) to 0.22 g/mL (*S. aureus*), while minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values ranged from 0.16 g/mL (*Dickeya solani* and *Bacillus cereus*) to 0.40 g/mL (*S. aureus*).

E. camaldulensis bark extract inhibited the proliferation of Gram-negative *Salmonella* spp. Sidkey and Omran (2017) found that *Streptococcus mutans* was more inhibited than *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis* at 50 mg/ml, while *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was more inhibited than *Salmonella* spp. and *E. coli*. The antibacterial activity of this plant may be attributed to the presence of phenols, flavonoids, tannins, and essential oils.

Ghareeb et al. (2018) assessed the antimicrobial properties of *E. camaldulensis* leaves. Water and ethyl acetate (EtOAc) extracts showed the strongest antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Candida albicans*, and *Aspergillus niger*. Vacuum liquid chromatography (VLC) of the EtOAc extract yielded 13 fractions, of which fractions 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 exhibited antibacterial activity. Fractions 5 and 6 showed the most pronounced antibacterial activity, with inhibition zones ranging from 5 to 14 mm. Chromatography of the EtOAc extract identified six compounds: hesperidin (6), luteolin (5), quercetin (4), methyl gallate (3), gallic acid (1), and taxifolin (2). These phenolic compounds may contribute to the potent antibacterial properties of *E. camaldulensis* leaf extract and may be useful in managing schistosomiasis and treating bacterial infections.

Asiaei and Fakoor (2018) isolated essential oil from *E. camaldulensis* leaves and found that *Klebsiella pneumoniae* demonstrated the highest susceptibility, with an inhibition zone diameter of 35 mm and MIC and MBC values of 500 and 1500 ppm, respectively. *Salmonella infantis* and *Salmonella enteritidis* were the least affected,

with an inhibition zone diameter of 11 mm and MIC and MBC values of 6,000 and 8,000 ppm, respectively. The main constituent of the essential oil was identified as 1,8-cineole (55.2%). Chaves et al. (2018) suggested that *E. camaldulensis* essential oil (EOEc) may regulate resistance to β -lactam antibiotics in strains of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) and β -lactamase-producing bacteria. The oil contained predominantly 1,8-cineole (76.93%), β -pinene (11.49%), and α -pinene (7.15%). Some *S. aureus* strains exhibited resistance to the oil's antibacterial properties (MIC = 1000 g mL⁻¹). Ishag et al. (2018) tested *E. camaldulensis* leaf extracts in water, ethanol, chloroform, ethyl acetate, and petroleum ether against *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, and *S. aureus*. Leaf extracts demonstrated efficacy against these bacteria at high concentrations (100 and 50 mg/mL), with inhibition zone diameters ranging from 11 to 35 mm.

Nasr et al. (2019) reported that *E. camaldulensis* crude extracts produced a wide range of inhibitory zones ($p < 0.01$). The crude extract from capsules (30% acetone) significantly inhibited the growth of *A. baumannii* (35 mm clear zone). Bacterial MICs against *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* ranged from 0.5 to 20 mg/m. Nwabor Vongkamjan and Voravuthikunchai (2019) investigated the inhibitory effect of *E. camaldulensis* leaf extract in ethanol on the foodborne bacterium *Listeria monocytogenes*. The extract contained 15.05 mg of quercetin per milligram and 11.10 mg of gallic acid per milligram of total phenolic and flavonoid contents, respectively. The extract exhibited a minimum bactericidal concentration of 256–512 μ g/mL and a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of 64–128 μ g/mL. Alghamdi and Ababutain (2019) evaluated the antibacterial activity of *E. camaldulensis* leaf and bark extracts against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *B. subtilis*. Both leaf and bark extracts inhibited all tested bacteria and contained tannin, saponins, flavonoids, carbohydrates, and proteins. Several compounds with antibacterial properties, including cyclononasiloxane, octadecamethyl-, 17-

Pentatriacontene, 4H-Pyran-4-one, 3,5-dihydroxy-2-methyl-, and phytol, were identified.

Munir et al. (2020) found that gum extract of *E. camaldulensis* was an effective bio-matrix for the green synthesis of nanoparticles. The resulting EC-ZnNPs and EC-AgNPs exhibited superior inhibitory effects against *E. coli* compared to gum samples and were shown to be non-mutagenic and non-toxic. Limam et al. (2020) reported that spathulenol, a major compound in *E. camaldulensis*, demonstrated the lowest minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC = 0.93 mg/mL) against *Serratia marcescens*, with a significant inhibition zone (25.33 2.84) and an efficacy concentration of 50% (EC50 = 2.96 0.11 mg/mL).

Ahmed et al. (2021) found that *E. camaldulensis* oil had the highest antibacterial activity against *S. typhimurium* (inhibition zone: 20.63 mm), followed by *E. coli* (inhibition zone: 19.43 mm). Qasim Omer and Yahya (2021) tested aqueous, ethanolic, and flavonoid extracts of *E. camaldulensis* against *Staphylococcus* using the β -lactamase enzyme assay and the biofilm formation test. Flavonoid extract of *E.*

camaldulensis showed higher potential as an antimicrobial agent on *S. aureus* than crude aqueous and ethanol extracts.

Hanif et al. (2021) evaluated extracts of *E. camaldulensis* against several bacteria, including *C. glutamicum*, *K. pneumonia*, *S. agalactiae*, *S. pyrogens*, *A. baumannii*, and *S. aureus*. The extracts exhibited varying MICs and MBCs against the tested bacteria.

Tine et al. (2022) found that the essential oil of *E. camaldulensis* leaf extract showed excellent activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *E. faecalis*, and moderate activity against *P. aeruginosa*.

Wunnoo et al. (2021) developed *E. camaldulensis* leaf extract (bio-AgNPs) as a potent anti-biofilm agent for the treatment of tissue infections. The formulation demonstrated broad-spectrum antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, significantly inhibiting biofilm formation in all examined pathogens. *E. camaldulensis* exhibits antibacterial qualities against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial species details of studies focused on antibacterial activities are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Antibacterial Activity of Eucalyptus Camaldulensis

Bacterial Strain	Extract Used	MIC	Reference
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	Oils extract from leaf	0.5-2ml	(Knezevic et al., 2016)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> , <i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Leaf extract	50mg/27mm	(Chuku et al., 2016)
<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i> , <i>Pectobacterium carotovorum</i> , <i>Agrobacterium tumefaciens</i>	Bark extract	20.0mm-18.3mm	(Mervat et al., 2017)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Streptococcus</i> and <i>Bacillus</i> (Gram positive), <i>Escherichia coli</i> (Gram negative)	Leave and fruit oil	p<0.05	(Dogan et al., 2017)
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Leaf extract	0.16ug/ml-0.40ug/ml	(Elansary et al., 2017)
<i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>Escherichia coli</i>	Bark extract	40, 50mg/ml	(Sidkey and Omran, 2017)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>Salmonella infantis</i> , <i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Oil extract from leaf	35 mm	(AsiaeiMoghimpour and Fakoor, 2018)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Oils extract from leave	1000 μ g mL ⁻¹	(Chaves et al., 2018)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Leaf extract	100 and 50mg/ml	(Ishag et al., 2018)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	Capsule crude extract	35mm	(Nasr et al., 2019)
<i>Monocytogenes</i>	Leaf extract	p<0.05	(NwaborVongkamjan and Voravuthikunchai,

			2019)
Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Escherichia coli, Bacillus subtilis, Staphylococcus aureus	Leaf and bark extract	-	(Alghamdi and Ababutain, 2019)
Serratia marcescens	Leaf oil	0.93mg/ml	(Limam et al., 2020)
Streptococcus mutans, Lactobacillus rhamnosus, Actinomyces viscosus	Leaf oil	-	(Qasim Omer and Yahya, 2021)
S. typhimurium, E. coli, L. monocytogene	Leaf oil	20.63mm, 19.43mm, 19.21mm	(Hamed et al., 2021)
Klebsiella pneumonia, Acinetobacter baumannii, Corynebacterium, Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus pyrogens, Streptococcus agalactiae	Leaf oil	First three 6.25ug/ml And last three are 12.5 ug/ml	(Hanif et al., 2021)
S. aureus, E. coli, E. faecalis. P. aeruginosa	leaf Oil	25.3 ± 1.2mm; 18.7 ± 0.6mm; 17.8 ± 0.3mm	(Tine et al., 2022)

Antifungal Activity

The growth of fungal hyphae of five common mould fungi—*Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium subglutinans*, *Chaetomium globosum*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Trichoderma viride*—on *E. camaldulensis* wood surface was inhibited by essential oil extracted from *E. camaldulensis* leaves (Salem et al., 2016). The oil, containing eucalyptol (60.32%), α -pinene (13.65%), and γ -terpinene (8.77%), completely inhibited the growth of *A. alternata*, *F. subglutinans*, *C. globosum*, and *A. niger*. GakuubiMaina and Wagacha (2017) demonstrated the fungicidal properties of *E. camaldulensis* essential oils against *Fusarium* species, with minimum fungicidal concentrations of 8–10 μ L/mL and minimum inhibitory concentrations of 7–8 μ L/mL.

Dogan et al. (2017) investigated the chemical makeup of essential oils from *E. camaldulensis* fruit and leaves and their antifungal qualities. Oils demonstrated fungicidal effect against *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida glabrata*. Leaf essential oils exhibited more activity than fruit essential oils. Leaf extracts from *E. camaldulensis* were found to be effective against *Candida albicans*, with significant growth reduction observed at high dosages (100 and 50 mg/mL) (Ishag et al., 2018). Üstüner et al. (2018) showed that essential oils from *E. camaldulensis* significantly influenced the growth of fungal mycelia of several fungal species.

Nasr et al. (2019) reported that *E. camaldulensis* crude extracts exhibited significant antifungal

activity, with *Rhizopus stolonifer* showing the greatest inhibition (96% reduction in radial growth).

Ez-Zriouli et al. (2019) ascertained the chemical makeup and antifungal efficacy of *E. camaldulensis* essential oil against *Fusarium culmorum* and *Fusarium solani*. The essential oil completely stopped the growth of both fungi, exhibiting a very considerable level of efficiency.

Elgat et al. (2020) demonstrated the broad-spectrum antifungal effects of *E. camaldulensis* essential oil against common mould fungi (*Aspergillus flavus*, *A. niger*, *A. terreus*, and *Fusarium culmorum*).

Salem et al. (2016) found that pulp prepared from *E. camaldulensis* wood branches with different additives has antifungal qualities. Etemadi Moghadam and Yousefi (2020) highlighted the effectiveness of *E. camaldulensis* essential oil, primarily composed of 1, 8-cineole (36.62%), in suppressing *C. albicans*. Munir et al. (2020) demonstrated that zinc and silver nanoparticles (EC-ZnNPs and EC-AgNPs) derived from *E. camaldulensis* gum extract effectively inhibited the fungus *Schizophyllum commune*. Wunnoo et al. (2021) reported that *E. camaldulensis* leaf extract-derived bio-AgNPs exhibited strong fungicidal action against *Candida* biofilms and may also serve as an antioxidant.

Taha et al. (2021) investigated the effects of *E. camaldulensis* leaf (ECL) and flower bud (ECF) extracts on the antifungal properties of paper sheets made from linen fiber pulp. Paper sheets

treated with ECL and ECF hindered the growth of *A. niger*, *A. terreus*, and *F. culmorum*. Al-Shahwany and Shoker (2021) observed the highest inhibitory effects of *E. camaldulensis* essential oil on *A. niger*, *A. flavus*, and *Penicillium* sp. SomdaLeth and Sereme (2017) assessed the in vitro inhibitory activity of *E. camaldulensis* against *F. moniliforme*, *Phoma sorghina*, and *Colletotrichum graminicola*. Caetano et al. (2022) evaluated the in vitro and in vivo antifungal effects of free and nano-encapsulated *E. camaldulensis* essential oils against the fungus *Hemileia vastatrix*. Nanoparticles containing 1,8-cineol exhibited 100% in vitro antifungal activity.

Antiviral Activity

Studies have shown that Eucalyptus essential oil and its main monoterpenes have significant potential for preventing and treating virally induced infectious diseases. The primary mechanism of antiviral action involves direct inactivation through the binding of monoterpenes to free viruses, particularly viral proteins involved in host cell entry and penetration (Mieres-Castro et al., 2021).

Al-Hadih et al. (2016) investigated the antiviral qualities of the polyphenolic components of *E. camaldulensis* bark extract (ECBE) against Newcastle Disease Virus (NDV). *E. camaldulensis* extracts demonstrated full inhibition of NDV. Abu-Jafar and Huleihel (2017) assessed the antiviral properties of *E. camaldulensis* leaf extract against herpes viruses. The 80%-MeOH fraction of the extract exhibited the most potent antiviral activity against varicella-zoster virus (VZV) and herpes simplex virus-1 and 2 (HSV-1, HSV-2).

Insecticidal activity

The increasing concerns regarding the environmental and health hazards associated with synthetic pesticides have spurred research into plant-based alternatives for pest management. *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* Dehnhardt (Myrtaceae), commonly known as the river red gum, is a widely distributed tree species known for its diverse pharmacological properties,

including significant insecticidal activity. This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the documented insecticidal effects of *E. camaldulensis* EOs and extracts against various insect pests.

Insecticidal Activity Against Stored Product Pests
Several studies have evaluated the efficacy of *E. camaldulensis* against key pests of stored agricultural commodities:

Rice Weevil (*Sitophilus oryzae*): *E. camaldulensis* oil exhibited strong insecticidal efficacy against *S. oryzae* adults with LC₅₀ values of 22.22 and 36.57 $\mu\text{L/L}$ in fumigation assays (El-Bakry et al., 2016). Furthermore, *E. camaldulensis* EOs and their constituents demonstrated repellent effects on adult *S. oryzae* in olfactometer studies, with some binary and ternary combinations showing synergistic repellent activity (Hategekimana and Erler, 2020). Contact and fumigant procedures in vitro also showed high mortality rates for *S. oryzae* at concentrations of 20 ppm (61.66% mortality in fumigation) and complete mortality at all tested concentrations (1, 5, 10, 20, and 30 ppm) in contact assays after 24 hours (Abdelkhalek et al., 2020).

Rust Red Flour Beetle (*Tribolium castaneum*): *E. camaldulensis* oil showed insecticidal activity against *T. castaneum* adults with an LC₅₀ value of 36.57 $\mu\text{L/L}$ (El-Bakry et al., 2016). Fumigant assays also revealed a 61.66% mortality rate at 20 ppm (Abdelkhalek et al., 2020). Additionally, the mortality rates of *T. castaneum* increased with increasing concentration and exposure duration to *E. camaldulensis* EOs (ElnabawyHassan and Taha, 2021).

Lesser Grain Borer (*Rhyzopertha dominica*): *E. camaldulensis* essential oil displayed notable insecticidal properties against *R. dominica* (Idouarame et al., 2018).

Khapra Beetle (*Trogoderma granarium*): Adults of *T. granarium* were found to be more susceptible to *E. camaldulensis* EOs than immature stages. In choice tests, both larvae and adults preferred untreated wheat seeds over those treated with *E. camaldulensis* EOs at LC₂₀ or LC₅₀ concentrations. The application of these EOs to wheat seeds reduced the number of damaged seeds and seed weight loss in a dose-

dependent manner (BorzouiKhaghani and Nouri-Ganbalani, 2021).

Maize Weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais*): *E. camaldulensis* leaf powder exhibited a 100% repellence effect at a dosage of 2.0 g/20 g of maize seeds and 65% toxicity at 1.0 g/20 g after 96 hours of exposure, suggesting its potential as a substitute for synthetic pesticides in stored maize (EmekaEwete and Ebeniro, 2020).

Cowpea Weevil (*Callosobruchus maculatus*): Methanol, hexane, and acetone extracts of *E. camaldulensis* leaves demonstrated efficacy against *C. maculatus*. The hexane extract (5g/kg) was the most effective, causing 78.75% mortality and completely inhibiting F1 offspring development, providing seed protection for three months (Mahama et al., 2018).

Insecticidal Activity Against Agricultural Pests

Mango Mealybug (*Drosicha mangiferae*): Leaf-dip and twig-dip methods using *E. camaldulensis* essential oil showed insecticidal activity against adult females and second-instar nymphs of *D. mangiferae* infesting citrus crops. Aqueous, ethanol, and acetone extracts were effective against nymphs, with ethanol extracts showing significant toxicity (Majeed et al., 2018). Ethanol extracts of *E. camaldulensis* exhibited the lowest LC50 values against this mealybug.

Black Bean Aphid: An aqueous extract of *E. camaldulensis* (50% concentration by infusion) demonstrated the highest aphicidal activity, causing 93% mortality after 12 hours and exhibiting a remarkable 70% repellency rate against adult aphids at the same concentration (Mouna et al., 2021).

Insecticidal Activity Against Disease Vectors and Nuisance Insects

Mosquitoes (*Aedes aegypti* and *Anopheles gambiae*): *E. camaldulensis* essential oil demonstrated 13.7% mosquito-repellent activity against female *Ae. aegypti* at a concentration of 30 g/cm² (Azeem et al., 2019). The EOs also exhibited larvicidal activity against *Ae. aegypti* larvae, with a comparable LC50 value of 33.7 ppm (Manh et al., 2020; Yaméogo et al., 2021). Furthermore, *E. camaldulensis* EOs irritated adults of both *Ae. aegypti* and *An. gambiae*, with repellent-irritant effects on *An. gambiae*

remarkably similar to DEET (Balboné et al., 2023). Combinations of ethanoic leaf extracts and essential oils of *E. camaldulensis* and *Callistemon rigidus* showed 100% mortality against third- and fourth-instar larvae of *An. gambiae* (Younoussa et al., 2020).

German Cockroach (*Blattella germanica*): First-instar nymphs were more susceptible than adults to the fumigant and contact toxicity of *E. camaldulensis* EOs. The LC50 values for applied surface toxicity, fumigant toxicity, and dipping toxicity ranged from 15.01 to 28.80 µL/L, 2202.8 to 5600.2 mg/L, and 9484.2 to 34,421.1 mg/L, respectively, with fumigant and dipping methods proving significantly more toxic (Moharrampour and Rezaei Khaghani, 2019).

House Fly (*Musca domestica*): *E. camaldulensis* EOs demonstrated significant toxicity against *M. domestica* larvae (LC50 = 277.01 ppm), pupae (LC50 = 164.87 ppm), and adults (LC50 = 302.75 ppm). The EOs also exhibited strong repellency (72.80%) and oviposition deterrence (89.13%) against house flies (Khan et al., 2021).

Impact on Beneficial Insects

Parasitoid Wasp (*Habrobracon hebetor*): Fumigant toxicity studies on adult female *H. hebetor* revealed LC50 values of 1.116, 0.34, and 3.416 µL/L air for different *E. camaldulensis* essential oils. These EOs significantly impacted the intrinsic rate of increase (*r*), finite rate of growth (*λ*), net reproductive rate (R0), and gross reproductive rate (GRR) of the parasitoid (Razmjou et al., 2018). This highlights the importance of considering the non-target effects of *E. camaldulensis* EOs in pest management strategies.

Chemical Composition and Mode of Action for insecticidal activity

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis of *E. camaldulensis* bark extract revealed the presence of various polyphenolic components, including benzoic acid, quinol, salicylic acid, myricetin, and rutin (Abdelkhalik et al., 2020). These compounds, individually or synergistically, are likely responsible for the observed insecticidal activities. The modes of action reported in the reviewed studies include

contact toxicity, fumigant toxicity, repellency, and oviposition deterrence, suggesting a complex interplay of physiological and behavioral effects on target insects. The reviewed literature provides compelling evidence for the significant insecticidal potential of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* essential oils and extracts against a diverse array of insect pests affecting stored products, agriculture, and human health. The demonstrated efficacy through various application methods and the diverse modes of action highlight the promise of *E. camaldulensis* as a source of environmentally friendly biopesticides. However, further research is warranted to optimize extraction and formulation techniques, elucidate the specific bioactive compounds and their mechanisms of action, and comprehensively assess the non-target effects on beneficial organisms to ensure the sustainable and responsible application of *E. camaldulensis*-based pest management strategies

Anticancer activity

The search for novel and effective anticancer agents from natural sources has gained significant momentum. *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* Dehnhardt, a widely cultivated tree, has been investigated for its diverse pharmacological properties, including its potential to combat cancer. This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the current research on the anticancer properties of *E. camaldulensis* extracts and essential oils.

Studies have demonstrated the cytotoxic effects of *E. camaldulensis* against various human cancer cell lines: The P19 embryonal cancer stem cell line showed increased susceptibility to the cytotoxic effects of *E. camaldulensis* extract compared to *Circhorium intybus* (Soltanian Sheikhabaei and Mohamadi, 2017), suggesting potential targeting of cancer stem cells.

Aqueous extract of *E. camaldulensis* leaves (AEECL) was utilized to synthesize colloidal nanosilver (CN-Ag), which exhibited high cytotoxicity against human colon cancer cells (Caco-2) at low concentrations (5 µg/mL) (Zein et al., 2022). *E. camaldulensis* essential oil demonstrated anticancer effects against the Caco-

2 colorectal cancer cell line, with a half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of 100 µg/mL. Treatment with the essential oil also significantly upregulated the expression of the pro-apoptotic gene BAX and downregulated the anti-apoptotic gene BCL-2 (Taheiri et al., 2020). Both ethanolic (EE) and aqueous (AE) extracts of *E. camaldulensis* exhibited cytotoxic effects on human alveolar adenocarcinoma basal epithelial cells (A549) and breast cancer cell line (MCF-7). Notably, AE contained a higher concentration of active substances and showed greater antioxidant activity compared to EE (Nasser et al., 2020). Ethanolic extract of *E. camaldulensis* significantly delayed the development of the MCF-7 breast cancer cell line in a concentration-dependent manner, with cytotoxic activity increasing with concentration (Mohammed et al., 2021). Plant extracts of *E. camaldulensis* used in the synthesis of nanoparticles demonstrated potent anticancer effects and high selectivity for various human cancer cell lines, with anticancer properties generally showing concentration dependence (TadeleAbire and Feyisa, 2021).

The combination of *E. camaldulensis* extracts with conventional chemotherapeutic agents has shown synergistic effects: The addition of both ethanolic (EE) and aqueous (AE) extracts of *E. camaldulensis* to low-dose cisplatin (CDDP) significantly accelerated cell death in A549 and MCF-7 cells compared to treatment with CDDP alone (Nasser et al., 2020).

Extracts from *E. camaldulensis* leaves demonstrated the ability to prevent skin cancer development in an in vivo model. The extract significantly and dose-dependently reduced both the incidence and the number of tumors per animal (Alzoubi et al., 2021). Antimutagenic activity was also observed through the reduction of sister chromatid exchange (SCE) levels.

Phytochemical Constituents and Potential Mechanisms

Phytochemical screening of *E. camaldulensis* ethanolic extract revealed the presence of various bioactive compounds, including tannins, saponins, phenolic compounds, reducing sugars, terpenoids, steroids, glucosides, alkaloids, and

flavonoids (Mohammed et al., 2021). The essential oil of *E. camaldulensis* was found to be rich in monoterpenoid hydrocarbons (36%) and oxygenated monoterpenes (22.3%), with β -pinene (16.5%) and 1,8-cineole (17.1%) as the major components, along with significant levels of limonene, β -eudesmol, and α -pinene (Grewsal et al., 2022). While 1,8-cineole exhibited the lowest cytotoxicity among the tested components ($CC_{50} > 640 \mu\text{g/mL}$), the essential oil itself showed higher cytotoxicity ($CC_{50} > 20 \mu\text{g/mL}$), suggesting potential synergistic effects of its constituents. The phytochemicals present in *E. camaldulensis* extracts are also believed to contribute to the selectivity of synthesized nanoparticles towards cancer cells (TadeleAbire and Feyisa, 2021).

Oral health

Eucalyptus camaldulensis exhibits significant potential in promoting oral health due to its inherent antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory characteristics. The essential oil of this species, with 1,8-cineole constituting the majority of its chemical composition (36.62%), demonstrates potent antibacterial activity against key microorganisms implicated in dental caries, namely *Streptococcus mutans*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, and *Actinomyces viscosus* (Etemadi et al., 2020; EtemadiMoghadam and Yousefi, 2020). Furthermore, *E. camaldulensis* essential oil displays adequate antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* (Etemadi et al., 2020). Consequently, extracts from *Eucalyptus* species, including *E. camaldulensis*, are commonly incorporated into various oral hygiene products such as mouthwashes and anti-plaque chewing gum, effectively combating a range of oral pathogens including *A. niger*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *S. typhimurium*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. sobrinus*, *S. mutans*, and *Haemophilus* (Dogan et al., 2017). Indeed, *E. camaldulensis* is a major component in numerous consumer goods, including toothpastes and mouthwashes (Ishag et al., 2018). Notably, its effectiveness in treating gingivitis and supragingival dental plaque has been demonstrated in over 24 trials, showing an average reduction of 18% and 25%, respectively,

when compared to placebo and other mouthwashes (Gbekley et al., 2017; Salehi et al., 2019). A clinical study involving human volunteers found that a eucalyptus oil-containing mouthwash, used twice daily, resulted in a comparable reduction in plaque levels (1.008 ± 0.27) and gingival index scores (1.233 ± 0.72) after 14 days to a chlorhexidine mouthwash used once daily (plaque index: 1.012 ± 0.25 ; gingival index: 1.254 ± 0.58), without any reported adverse side effects (RagulDhanraj and Jain, 2018). These findings underscore the potential of eucalyptus oil as a viable alternative to chlorhexidine for maintaining proper oral hygiene and suggest its utility in developing antimicrobial medications for treating dental caries and other infectious oral diseases (EtemadiMoghadam and Yousefi, 2020)

Respiratory Diseases

Eucalyptus camaldulensis has a long history of traditional use in treating various respiratory ailments, a practice supported by its rich profile of bioactive chemicals, including sterols, terpenoids, saponins, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds (Shayoub¹ et al., 2015). The high concentration of 1,8-cineole (ranging from 15% to 78%) found in its leaves is particularly significant, as this compound has been shown to promote respiration, relieve coughing, and facilitate mucus expulsion, making *E. camaldulensis* a remedy for conditions such as bronchitis, asthma, catarrh, sinusitis, and throat infections (Diriye et al., 2017). Traditionally, decoctions made primarily from the leaves and roots were administered orally (Gbekley et al., 2017), and even the dried leaves were smoked like tobacco to alleviate asthma (Hussain et al., 2020). In vitro evaluations of *E. camaldulensis*'s ability to combat *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, the causative agent of tuberculosis, have shown minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) ranging from 6.25 to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for various extracts (Elhassan et al., 2017), and its extracts have also demonstrated greater cytotoxicity against lung tumor cells compared to single extracts (Çetintaş et al., 2020). Furthermore, ethanol extracts of *E. camaldulensis* have shown

efficacy in inhibiting the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from nasal carriers (QasimOmer and Yahya, 2021), and were found to be more cytotoxic to lung cancer cells than other extracts, even exhibiting an additional cytotoxic effect when combined with low-dose cisplatin (Nasser et al., 2020). Animal studies indicate that while inhaled eucalyptus oil did not cause pathogenic changes, both consumed and inhaled oil can affect the respiratory system, with oral consumption leading to weight loss and altered hematological parameters; however, eucalyptus oil's ability to expand the tracheal lumen and reduce mucus secretion supports its use in treating respiratory ailments like sinusitis, obstructive pulmonary disease, asthma, cough, and common colds (Alnaji and Ali 2021). Notably, *E. camaldulensis* extracts obtained using deep eutectic solvents (DESs) showed superior inhibitory effectiveness against multidrug-resistant (MDR) *M. tuberculosis* compared to conventional water extracts, with DES2 exhibiting the strongest activity (MIC of 12.5 mg/mL and MBC of 50 mg/mL) (Dheyab et al., 2022). This species is also recognized for its use in treating a range of veterinary respiratory conditions, including influenza, bronchitis, and pneumonia (Madisha and McGaw, 2023).

Anti-diabetic Activity

Eucalyptus camaldulensis has demonstrated potential in managing diabetes through various mechanisms. Studies have shown that the leaves of *E. camaldulensis* possess strong antioxidant activity, effectively counteracting palmitic acid-induced insulin resistance in muscle cells. Furthermore, treatment with these leaf extracts enhanced the glucose uptake capacity of muscle cells, suggesting that *E. camaldulensis* may improve insulin signal transduction and glucose metabolism by reducing oxidative stress (Safina et al., 2016). In vivo studies using an oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) revealed that the crude hexane extract of *E. camaldulensis* had a significant hypoglycemic effect, notably lowering the glycaemic peak compared to the control. The active hypoglycemic compounds identified in this extract were hexadecanoic and octadecanoic acids

present in a specific ratio and as pure compounds (Daley et al., 2016). However, investigations into the effects of stem bark and leaf extracts on the blood glucose and lipid profiles of albino rats suggested that *E. camaldulensis* might enhance glucose bioavailability in circulation rather than directly preventing diabetes, while also indicating possible anti-lipidemic activity (Musa et al., 2019). In vitro studies have further elucidated a potential mechanism for glucose homeostasis through the inhibition of the α -glucosidase enzyme by *E. camaldulensis*. The essential oil of *E. camaldulensis* inhibited α -glucosidase in a concentration-dependent manner, with inhibition ranging from $6.08 \pm 1.89\%$ to $75.38 \pm 2.09\%$ at concentrations of 3.125 to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. Notably, the α -glucosidase inhibitory capacity of *E. camaldulensis* essential oil (IC₅₀ value: $12.04 \pm 3.17 \mu\text{g/mL}$) was found to be almost identical to that of the established anti-diabetic drug acarbose. The presence of 1,8-cineole in *E. camaldulensis* essential oil is considered a contributing factor to its anti-diabetic potential (Ahamad and Uthirapathy, 2021).

Analgesic properties

Eucalyptus camaldulensis exhibits significant analgesic properties, supported by both traditional use and scientific investigation. Its oil possesses anti-inflammatory effects and is believed to improve blood flow, thereby alleviating joint and muscular pain (Dhakad et al., 2018). Traditional Aboriginal medicine has a long-standing practice of using topical ointments containing eucalyptus oil to promote wound healing and address various ailments. For millennia, Aboriginal people have prepared bandages from *Eucalyptus* leaves and applied them to cuts, wounds, infections, and areas of joint pain (Chandorkar et al., 2021). Scientific evaluation of the essential oil from *E. camaldulensis* leaves, through molecular docking studies against cyclooxygenase 2, tumor necrosis factor- α , and interleukin-1 β convertase using Autodock Vina, suggests a potential mechanism for its analgesic qualities (Modal et al., 2021). Furthermore, in vivo studies have demonstrated

significant analgesic efficacy of *E. camaldulensis* in the writhing test. The essential oil also significantly increased the latency duration in hot-plate and tail immersion experiments, indicative of its pain-relieving effects. Additionally, the administration of *E. camaldulensis* essential oil resulted in a dramatic reduction in the number of licks during the formalin-induced paw licking test, further substantiating its strong analgesic properties (Modal et al., 2021). These findings collectively highlight the potential of *E. camaldulensis* as a source of natural analgesic agents.

Conclusions and recommendations

Eucalyptus camaldulensis has demonstrated remarkable health benefits, leading to its utilization in both medicinal and commercial sectors. Beyond its antiviral bioactivities against viruses such as Varicella-Zoster Virus, Newcastle Disease Virus (NDV), Herpes Simplex virus, and Tobacco Mosaic virus, *E. camaldulensis* exhibits significant antibacterial, antimicrobial, antifungal, and insecticidal properties, particularly in contact and fumigant applications against various insects and pests of stored products. Its antibacterial efficacy has been documented across numerous bacterial species, including *A. alternata*, *F. subglutinnans*, *C. globosum*, *A. niger*, *T. viride*, *C. tropicalis*, *C. globosum*, *C. albicans*, *V. dahliae*, *F. oxysporum*, *P. debaryanum*, *S. sclerotiorum*, *R. solani*, *R. stolonifer*, *F. culmorum*, *F. solani*, *A. flavus*, *A. terreus*, *S. commune*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *P. sorghina*, *C. graminicola*, *penicillium*, and *Cryptococcus albidus*. As a natural insect repellent, *E. camaldulensis* has proven effective against a wide range of insects, including *S. oryzae*, *Tribolium castaneum*, *D. mangiferae*, *H. hebetor*, *S. avenae*, *R. dominica*, *C. maculatus*, *B. germanica*, *A. Aegypti*, *O. surinamensis*, *C. rigidus*, *S. zeamais*, *Aphis fabae*, *Ae. Aegypti*, *T. granarium*, *M. domestica*, and *A. gambia*, positioning it as a viable alternative to synthetic insect repellents. Furthermore, extracts and oils from *E. camaldulensis* have shown promise in treating various cancers, including lung, breast, skin, and colon cancers, as well as

human colon cells and cancer stem cells (CSCs). Its antibacterial properties have also led to its incorporation in oral hygiene products such as mouthwash and toothpaste, as well as in softeners, pomades, and antitussive syrups. In the realm of respiratory health, *E. camaldulensis* essential oils and extracts have been utilized as a natural treatment for conditions like colds, asthma, and respiratory tract infections, with inhalation demonstrating bronchodilator effects and the potential to reduce airway inflammation. Additionally, the analgesic qualities of *E. camaldulensis* can be harnessed to relieve pain associated with headaches, arthritis, and muscle soreness through topical application of essential oil-containing ointments. This positions *E. camaldulensis* as a potentially safer and more environmentally friendly alternative to synthetic agents in treating bacterial, viral, insecticidal, and fungal diseases. It is recommended that further therapeutic research, particularly on Pakistani species, be conducted to fully leverage the advantageous traits of *E. camaldulensis*. Its diverse beneficial qualities have already led to its use in various products globally, including mouthwashes, toothpastes, antifungal paper sheets, antimicrobial-coated sutures, medications, and cosmetics.

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